

Effect of SiC additive in reaction sintering of bauxite and titania

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Raw bauxite and titania with molar ratio of Al_2O_3 : TiO_2 as 1.2 : 1 were mixed with varying amounts of SiC. The compacted powder was sintered at different temperatures in the range 1400–1500°. Magnitude of sintering and properties of the sintered compacted mass were found to be influenced by the SiC additive.

Aluminium titanate possesses a favorable combination of physical and chemical properties and it has important engineering applications. Djambazov *et al.*¹ synthesized Al_2TiO_5 at 1500° incorporating CaF_2 , La_2O_3 , SiO_2 or kaolin and MgO additives and studied its stabilization. Perera *et al.*² prepared aluminium titanate in stoichiometric ratio without additives and with 5 wt. % addition of MgO, Fe_2O_3 or SiO_2 . Pereira and Baldo³ showed that the production of Al_2TiO_5 phase requires special case in the stoichiometry in order to avoid spontaneous decomposition into the constituent oxides. Joe *et al.*⁴ studied structural changes and coordination in Al and Ti in the sol-gel derived aluminium titanate system as a function of temperature (65–1400°). Montoya *et al.*⁵ prepared a series of Al_2O_3 - TiO_2 mixed oxides and the single oxides were prepared by the sol-gel method. Uribe and Baudin⁶ obtained aluminium titanate from equimolar mixtures of high purity and fine grained Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 powders and the influence of the microstructures of the obtained compacts on the milling efficiency were studied. Low and Shi⁷ investigated the effects of beta-spodumene ($\text{Li}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{SiO}_2$) and zirconia additives on the physical and thermal characteristics of aluminium titanate ceramics. De Arenas *et al.*⁸ studied the effect of V_2O_5 , Na_2O , CaO and FeTiO_3 on the stabilization of Al_2TiO_5 . Sstanciu *et al.*⁹ simultaneously sintered and reacted sol-gel amorphous powders to form Al_2TiO_5 . Alecu and Stead¹⁰ observed that aluminium titanate is highly anisotropic in thermal expansion.

In the present investigation, role of SiC as an additive on the sintering of raw bauxite and titania mixture for the formation of aluminium titanate was studied.

Results and discussion

The molar ratio of Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 was kept as 1.2 : 1. The specific surface area of the raw material powders was $120 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which was sufficient enough for better compac-

tion. The DTA curves (figures not shown) of bauxite and titania show an endothermic peak at 300° and reveals non-existence of either endothermic or exothermic peak, respectively. The shrinkage of the compacts during sintering (Fig. 1) was mainly due to expulsion of the residual water from the mixture and the products crystallize from the amorphous part within the temperature range 1400–1500°. The increase

Fig. 1. Variation of volume shrinkage with temperature.

of firing shrinkage might be due to grain growth of the respective crystalline phases. With the increase of the additive, the extent of shrinkage decreases which might be due to higher refractory nature of the oxides. Apparent porosity values (Fig. 2) of the sintered compacts were found to decrease with the increase of SiC content which might be cor-

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent porosity with temperature

related with the conversion of SiC to active silica in an oxidizing atmosphere contributing to the liquid phase. But still then sufficient quantity of porosity was retained in the sintered product due to the presence of excess alumina than the conventional mullite. Gradual increase of bulk density (Fig. 3) with temperature indicates positive relation of sinterability with temperature. This was common to all the batches although the magnitude was different. From an analysis of true density values (Fig. 4), it can be concluded

Fig. 3. Variation of bulk density with temperature

Fig. 4. Variation of true density with temperature

that as the density increase occurred in steps, it was a clear indication of reaction sintering process and formation of aluminium titanate and densification occurred separately.

All the sintered products were subjected to thermal spalling, i.e. heating at 800° for 10 min and then quenched in air for 10 min, and the results are given in Table 1. It is observed from Table 1 that all the sample of the Batches I, II and III (Table 2) fired at 1400, 1450 and 1500°, could withstand 40 cycles without any visible cracks due to air-quenching and have much higher thermal shock resistance in comparison to Batch IV samples. The above spalling resistances might be due to the formation of low expansion titanate phase along with sharp grain boundaries with minimum glassy phase.

Table 1. Determination of spalling resistance of pellets fired at different temperatures

Firing temp. °C	Batch no	Number of cycles withstood	Remarks
1400	I	40	No crack
	II	40	No crack
	III	40	No crack
	IV	16	Cracked
1450	I	40	No crack
	II	40	No crack
	III	40	No crack
	IV	40	No crack
1500	I	40	No crack
	II	40	No crack
	III	40	No crack
	IV	38	Cracked

Table 2. Composition of the batches

Batch no	SiC g	Bauxite g	Titania g
I	0.0	88.31	28.44
II	1.17	89.43	28.17
III	3.39	85.66	27.59
IV	5.54	83.89	27.03

Variations of mechanical strength with temperature of firing for all the samples fired at 1500° show that Batch II samples has highest mechanical strength

From XRD diagrams of the samples (figures not shown), aluminium titanate was found to be the major crystalline phase in all the composition although mullite was also the major phase in Batch III samples. In addition, mullite was also detected as minor phase in Batch II samples whereas alumina was noted in all the four batches. The SEM analysis of Batch I samples (figures not shown) indicates distribution of titanate phase along with corundum with sharp grain boundary. With the introduction of SiC, the microstructure changed significantly with some needle shaped mullite crystals formed by secondary crystallization. The microstructure initially contained some sub-rounded particles, but with 3% SiC there was excessive growth which exhibited some trans-angular cracks in the microstructure. The growth disappeared with the increase of SiC content, which generated some glassy phase due to the release of SiO₂ from oxidation of SiC.

Conclusion

Low expansion aluminium titanate can be generated through the reaction sintering of bauxite and titania in the temperature range 1400–1500°. With the incorporation of SiC, the matrix becomes strengthened upto an optimum addition of 3% SiC, above which it imparts some deleterious effects in the microstructure. This might be due to *in situ* oxidation of SiC with the release of active silica, which generates mullite by secondary crystallization.

Experimental

Raw bauxite (Katni origin), TiO₂ (A R, 97.80%) and SiC (A R, 98.50%) were used as the starting material for the synthesis of aluminium titanate. The bauxite sample

was analyzed for SiO₂, 0.86, Al₂O₃, 59.49, Fe₂O₃, 2.45, TiO₂, 5.42, L O I, 30.15%

Required amount of raw bauxite and titania were taken in the molar ratio of Al₂O₃ : TiO₂ as 1.2 : 1 and SiC was added in various amounts. Compositions of the batches are given in Table 2.

DTA analysis was carried out with a Netzsch STA-409 analyzer. Infrared spectra (KBr) were carried out with a Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer (Magna IR series II). Pellets of the samples were fabricated at a pressure of 2000 kg/cm² in a hydraulic press without any extra binder. The pellets were sintered at 1400, 1450 and 1500° in an electrically heated muffle furnace with 2 h of soaking period. The heating rate of the pellets was 10°/min up to 1000° and then 5°/min to the final temperature of heat treatment. Apparent porosity, true density and density of the sintered compacts were measured following standard conventional procedure. Thermal spalling resistance of the samples was carried out by air quenching method. X Ray diffraction was recorded on a Philips PW-1730 diffractometer using CuK_α radiations. SEM photographs were taken by a S-440 Leo electron microscope.

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